

MODERN AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOLKLORE

Madinabonu Akhmedova

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5483-7872>
e-mail: art784@bk.ru

1University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences,
Tashkent, 100149, Republic of Uzbekistan
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Abstract: This article examines modern and innovative technologies in teaching folklore. Examples of folklore in higher education were and remain in traditional teaching; but at present these examples are taught more effectively with the help of innovative methods. Because modern methods and technologies begin with serious preparation. It should be noted that examples of folklore found in textbooks are used both as the main text and as an auxiliary one

Key words: folklore, modern and innovative technologies, teaching, storage

1 Introduction

Web service technology specialists have already developed the content of the so-called unified educational environment, which includes such important educational resources as electronic libraries, depositories of specific software, original lecture courses, collections of abstracts, term papers and theses, test assignment databases, etc.

The creation of various types and levels of electronic libraries is an urgent task for specialists working in the field of software for science, culture and education. This is evidenced, in particular, by numerous publications in the proceedings of scientific conferences and articles in world scientific journals [5]. A draft

Concept of the National Electronic Library has been developed [2]; there are examples of more or less successful creation of interlibrary catalogs in centralized library systems: the Library of Natural Sciences of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences grew out of the digital system [3]; a complex of software and hardware for the libraries of institutes and the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan has been created in order to unite them into a single network with Internet access [1]; several specialized regional libraries (for medicine, ecology, culture) are being formed on the platforms, as well as an educational server to support additional and professional education [4]. Experience shows that the creation of an electronic library for specialization in folklore studies can be carried out in two ways: as the creation of an autonomous electronic library and as a unification of the resources of electronic libraries of universities and research centers of Uzbekistan. In the first case, the following technologies can be considered for replenishing the collection:

In the second case, we are talking about the development of an interlibrary electronic catalog, the means of its creation and maintenance; forms of user access to it. The stage of creating electronic libraries on folklore studies should be preceded by extensive preparatory work (and, of course, the country's leading specialists should take part in it) to identify the range of textbooks, monographs, collections of articles and individual articles, various types of methodological manuals necessary for the effective solution of educational problems.

2 Experimental results and their discussion

Computer programs for preparing students for folklore practice. Currently, almost every major university in the country has its own programs for educational practice in folklore. The most interesting forms of field work by folklorists in the country are discussed annually at seminars held by teachers and researchers of oral folklore, and then published in a special edition. Based on the existing experience, specialists from the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, under the guidance of folklorist, Professor O.S. Kayumov, have developed a software and methodological complex that will allow students to learn how to qualitatively collect, process and structure expedition materials, and then create databases, training and testing programs for use in scientific research or the educational process. The first part of the software and methodological complex describes the existing methodological guidelines for collecting material and provides the ability to compile and edit questionnaires for expeditions. Questionnaires, in turn, are divided into genres. If it is necessary to answer a specific question in the questionnaire, the program searches through all questionnaires. As a result, the user receives a set of answers to the question, which are much easier to analyze later than when working with a full questionnaire. The practical significance of this part is that before the expedition, the student can review the materials of already conducted expeditions, find out what needs to be added or changed in the questionnaire for a particular genre. If there are no samples on his topic,

he can review a sample questionnaire, change the wording of the questions, add new or delete old questions, save the questionnaire on the computer or print out its contents.

Another task performed by the software and methodological complex is documenting and storing the material of folklore expeditions. After the expeditions, philologists can enter the material they brought into the database. To simplify the input, the user can select a questionnaire and enter only the prepared answers. If the expedition has the appropriate equipment (digital video camera, laptop), all information is immediately entered into the computer. But if such equipment is not available, it becomes necessary to transfer all the obtained material to electronic media. The software and methodological complex describe the methods and techniques for processing the available material, explains not only the principles of converting text and graphic information into electronic form (scanning), but also the methods of processing and editing it using the example of the programs Abbyy FineReader VS Adobe Acrobat. To obtain information on processing photographs and illustrations, you can use the material devoted to scanning and image processing. Computer capabilities for recording sound, as well as for superimposing effects on video and sound are shown. In addition, a section is presented that talks about the digitization and processing of sound and video. This section will help students independently (if they have the necessary hardware and software) process the available information brought from expeditions or found in relevant collections and archives, and structure it for presentation in a multimedia complex. The basis of such complexes is usually a printed text, which is supplemented by visual, sound and video materials, which also need to be processed.

The next task of the software and methodological complex is to teach students to independently create such multimedia complexes for their further use in the educational process. In this regard, the section of the software and methodological complex "WEB design" was developed, which presents the rules for placing and designing material for Internet projects: color design features, building a navigation system for the project, classifying educational sites posted on the Internet, popular thematic links to educational resources. Each topic is provided with graphic illustrations. There is sound accompaniment, there is a large set of examples that display the design features of Internet pages. As examples (in most cases), projects developed jointly by humanities and programmers were used. The software and methodological complex widely illustrate all the features of preparing and designing material intended for posting on the Internet. In addition to the software and methodological complex, a program is offered that allows students to independently generate texts for posting on the Internet. They enter only questions and a set of answers to them, and the program itself creates an Internet page. In addition, the complex includes already created projects for folklorists. They can be used as an example when structuring information and as a reference summary when selecting materials for a project. The created projects contain not only valuable materials from the university archive (text, audio, video, musical transcripts), but also testing programs for knowledge control. These projects are already used in the educational process.

Electronic databases. At present, no folklorist has any objections to the need to transfer field material to electronic media and create databases on their basis. In recent years, projects of this kind have been actively supported by the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences together with Professor O. Kayumov and his researchers. Indeed, their consistent implementation would allow researchers to get acquainted with previously practically inaccessible regional archives, identify areas of field work of folklorists, and carry out a full (in a comparative aspect) analysis of the tradition of interest. At the same time, the material collected and systematized by scientists becomes available to "a wide range of people interested in the current state of the folklore tradition and socio-cultural practices." Basic requirements for the creation of electronic databases are gradually being developed: they must ensure the storage of a large array of texts, photographs, audio and video recordings; quick access to them and retrieval of information. The question of the need to create full-text databases is increasingly being raised. However, there is no single approach to implementing this idea yet. At least three types of them are presented on the Internet:

Electronic lecture courses are quickly conquering the educational space. Their effectiveness is highly appreciated by both the authors and users. At the same time, it is generally recognized that "the transition to digital video is not only tactically but also economically feasible." Among the main requirements for video lectures, the following are usually named: high quality of media data, the presence of interactive systems, copyright protection.

The following types of electronic courses are equally interesting for specialization in folklore studies:

- 1) a full course in Russian or Uzbek folklore from one of the leading folklorists of the country's universities (there may be several such courses);
- 2) a course consisting of lectures by specialists in a particular field (for example, about folk theater, about ritual complexes, about a fairy tale, etc.);
- 3) a course consisting of preserved video fragments of lectures and speeches by leading world folklorists.

Electronic lecture courses can, and most likely should, be accompanied by illustrative material (sound anthologies, photos, etc.). Testing complexes can be developed on their basis.

Virtual laboratory. Electronic libraries and full-text databases can in turn become the basis for conducting humanitarian research focused on computer analysis of text, explication and modeling of semantic contexts of various types and levels.

3 Conclusions

In addition to the technical characteristics of the Web system, they also describe the areas of its own research prospects: replenishment of word form dictionaries, development of experimental, including quantitative methods for analyzing the word formation process, coverage of some issues in the history of natural language from the point of view of a potentially possible and currently implemented dictionary, analysis of the expressive potential of language forms, a new formulation of the problems of comparative linguistics. In addition, within its framework, analysis and modeling of micro-context (identification and analysis of various terminological fields within a sentence or an author's paragraph) and macro-context (identification and analysis of terminological fields within a work or their totality) are carried out. It seems that it is in this area that the idea of the fundamental nature of the educational process is most fully expressed. Students practically for the first time have the opportunity to apply in practice the knowledge obtained as a result of mastering mathematical courses (probabilistic and statistical methods, including cluster analysis, the basics of modeling, computer versification, etc.). Based on the available full-text databases, relying on the rich tradition of structural-typological and semiotic study of folklore, novice folklorists can continue research into the mechanisms of generation of folklore and cultural stereotypes (identification of traditional formulas, methods of their compatibility within one genre and tradition as a whole), the structure of individual genres (fairy tales, proverbs, riddles), the rhythm of folk lyrics. In the latter case, the technology of dynamic presentation of poetic texts can be used. Organization of such studies in the practice of training specialists in traditional culture contributes to a deeper assimilation of such complex concepts as "model", "structure", "function", "paradigm", etc., conscious use of the main methods of text analysis. As for the depositories of term papers and diploma papers, they should include a list of topics of term papers and diploma papers on folklore, completed in the country's universities, with a system of annotations.

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